

INFLUENCE OF PROCESS PARAMETERS ON THE EFFICIENCY OF TRANSVERSE IMPREGNATION OF TEXTILES

D. Becker¹, P. Mitschang¹

¹Institut für Verbundwerkstoffe GmbH
Erwin-Schrödinger-Str., Geb. 58, Kaiserslautern, Germany
Email: david.becker@ivw.uni-kl.de, web page: <http://www.ivw.uni-kl.de>

Keywords: LCM, permeability, compaction, transverse, textiles

ABSTRACT

Transverse impregnation is gaining popularity among Liquid Composite Molding processes. Compared to in-plane impregnation it bears the potential to strongly reduce flow path lengths. However, the transverse impregnation behavior of textiles results from a complex interaction of permeability and compaction behavior. During impregnation, the textiles are deformed, especially when pre-compaction is low. This deformation can strongly decrease the impregnation speed and therefore the textile behavior is crucial for process efficiency and stability. To exploit the full potential of transverse impregnation, the correlation between process parameters, such as the injection pressure, and the textile impregnation behavior has to be known.

In the presented study the influence of the pressure drop, the flow rate, and the flow acceleration on the textile behavior during saturated transverse flow are investigated with a system, which allows the measurement of the saturated transverse permeability while simultaneously an online monitoring of the pressure drop dependent compaction is possible. Within the study the reaction of the textiles to defined pressure drops and flow rates at different initial fiber volume contents was measured. A woven fabric (glass, twill 2/2, 390 g/m²) and a non-crimp fabric (glass, biaxial, ±45°, 444 g/m²) were examined.

For both textiles severe deformations could be measured in a pressure drop range from 0 to 5 bars. Increases of the pressure drop of several percentage points were observed and it was proven that a heterogeneous fiber volume content distribution occurs. The compaction is accompanied by a decrease of the transverse permeability in the range of an order of magnitude. Correspondingly, it could be shown that at some point the increase of the pressure drop does not necessarily lead to an increased flow rate. The increase of the flow rate stagnates and in some cases it is even reduced by the increased pressure drop.

1 INTRODUCTION

The group of Liquid Composite Molding (LCM) processes offers a wide range of process variants for the manufacturing of fiber reinforced polymer composite (FRPC) components of various shape or size. Process variants which provide a transverse impregnation of the textile gain in popularity, as they bear a great potential for the reduction of flow path lengths, e.g. for automotive body parts which have a relatively large surface but a rather small thickness. Common examples for such process variants are Compression/Advanced RTM, Film Stacking, Vacuum Assisted Resin Infusion with flow media as top layer and the Vacuum Assisted Process, which utilizes a semi-permeable membrane.

The description of the impregnation phase of these processes is relatively complex, because of the strong deformability of textile lay-ups in out-of-plane direction. The possible effect of this deformability is illustrated in Figure 1. During the injection phase, the resin pressure will partially supersede the preform and a zone of pure resin will emerge (Zone 1). When the resin impregnates the textile, this fluid pressure will drop from injection pressure to atmospheric pressure within the impregnated textile (Zone 2). This pressure drop will cause a complex interaction of textile compaction and impregnation behavior. Ahead of the flow front, the dry textile will be homogeneously compacted by the injection pressure. The compaction effects due to the transverse impregnation are referred to as hydrodynamic compaction.

Figure 1: Preform deformation during transverse impregnation.

As the simulation of in-plane impregnation is often based on the assumption of a rigid preform, the consideration of textile deformability is of utmost importance for the accuracy of transverse impregnation simulations. The complexity is further increased by the fact that the compaction behavior of textiles is very different in wet and dry state [1-6]. Nevertheless, several simulation models have been developed to describe e.g. the Compression RTM process [7, 8], the vacuum infusion process [9], or generally LCM processes [10] as well as thermoplast-based transverse impregnation processes [11]. The results of these simulations all show the necessity of consideration of textile deformability. However, of course these simulations can only be as good as the input which was used. Hence, this leads to further challenges.

To describe the textile impregnation behavior, in general the permeability is used, which quantifies the conductivity of a porous media for a fluid. It results from the law of Darcy, which describes the correlation of the volumetric flow Q , the flown-through cross section A , the pressure drop Δp , the flow length Δx , the fluid viscosity η , and the permeability K :

$$Q = - \frac{K \cdot A \cdot \Delta p}{\eta \cdot \Delta x} \quad (1)$$

The textile permeability strongly depends on the fiber volume content. However, the fiber volume content changes during transverse impregnation, depending on the fluid pressure. Consequently, the permeability also changes. This can be proven experimentally, e.g. by generating a transverse flow through a preform at different pressure drops and applying the law of Darcy for the calculation of the permeability. With this approach a dependence of the measured permeability on the injection pressure was already experimentally shown [12-14]. As a result, for an accurate simulation of transverse impregnation it is not sufficient to know only the permeability at different fiber volume contents, but also the hydrodynamic compaction behavior has to be known.

Within this study, a novel measurement system is used, which combines permeability and hydrodynamic compaction measurement in order to investigate the transverse impregnation behavior of two textiles and especially the influence of the process parameters pressure drop, flow rate, and flow acceleration on this behavior.

3 MATERIALS

Two standard textiles were investigated: A glass woven fabric (WF) and a glass non-crimp fabric (NCF). Microscopic images of both are shown in Figure 2. The material data is listed in Table 1.

Figure 2: Microscopic images of the woven fabric and the non-crimp fabric used within the study.

Textile	Specification	Superficial density	Direction	Singly ply superficial density	Linear density	Yarn density
		[g/m ²]		[g/m ²]	[tex]	[1/cm]
Schlösser und Cramer 3106 (short: WF)	Glass fiber woven fabric (plain)	390 (±5.1%)	warp	-	340	6
			weft	-	272	6.7
Saertex X-E-444 g/m ² -1270 mm (short: NCF)	Glass fiber non-crimp fabric (pillar)	444 (±5.2%)	45°	217	-	-
			90° ¹	3	-	-
			0° ¹	1	-	-
			-45°	217	-	-
			Sewing thread ²	6	7.6	-

¹Stabilization yarns for improvement of handling

²Material: PES, Gauge: 5.0 /inch, Stitching length: 2.6 mm

Table 1: Material data of the WF and the NCF.

As a measurement fluid rapeseed oil was used, for which the viscosity depending on the temperature was investigated using a Brookfield spindle-rheometer DV-II+ Pro with a LV1 spindle (about 73 mPas at 20 °C).

4 EXPERIMENTAL SET-UP

The study is based on a novel measurement system, which combines a saturated transverse permeability measurement with a simultaneous transverse compaction monitoring. The system is shown in Figure 3 as a photo and a CAD – cross section. The textile lay-up to be investigated is placed within the cavity, which is formed by a lower and an upper distribution media (perforated discs). These distribution media allow a pre-compaction to be set and ensure a purely transverse flow. A continuous, transverse flow of measurement liquid through the cavity is generated. To calculate the transverse permeability based on Eq. (1), the pressure before and after the textile lay-up is measured by pressure transducers. The flown-through cross section and the flow length are defined by the cavity. The viscosity of the measurement fluid is known and the flow rate is measured at the inlet with a flow meter. To realize the compaction monitoring, the lower distribution media is moveable and slightly suspended, so that it always maintains contact to the textile, even if a hydrodynamic compaction occurs while the textile is flown through. This displacement of the lower distribution

media is measured by three displacement sensors and allows the calculation of the exact total fiber volume content at every time of the measurement. Hence, the transverse impregnation behavior in terms of saturated permeability and hydrodynamic compaction behavior can be measured at different process conditions. More details about the patented system [15], its development and validation, as well as the measurement procedure can be found in [16], [17], and [6].

Figure 3: Experimental set-up for the measurement of the transverse impregnation behavior (saturated permeability and hydrodynamic compaction).

To investigate the influence of process parameters on the textile impregnation behavior, the woven fabric and the non-crimp fabric were characterized with the presented system. For each textile three different initial fiber volume contents were set (WF: 45.9 %, 50.3 %, 54.6 %; NCF: 44.1 %, 50.9 %, 55.1%) and for each initial fiber volume content three to four samples were tested.

During each measurement the pressure drop was stepwise increased. Each pressure drop level was held until equilibrium was reached and flow rate, pressure drop and compaction levelled off. The data captured in the following 10 s was used for permeability and fiber volume content calculation. To reduce the influence of handling each stack was compacted 15 times to the later initial fiber volume content, prior to the impregnation. This was done using a press tool with defined cavity frames.

5 RESULTS & DISCUSSION

5.1 Influence of pressure drop and flow rate on the transverse impregnation behavior

Figure 4 shows the hydrodynamic compaction of the woven fabric (WF) and the non-crimp fabric (NCF) at different pressure drops, starting from three different initial fiber volume contents. Three main statements can be derived from the data:

- Remarkable hydrodynamic compaction occurs, even at relatively low pressure drops. For example the smallest initial fiber volume content of the woven fabric is about 46 %, but at a pressure drop of 4 bar about 52 % fiber volume were measured in the experiments.
- Hydrodynamic compaction occurs mainly after the pre-compaction is exceeded. For example the experiments at the highest initial fiber volume content for the NCF do not show any remarkable hydrodynamic compaction.
- The pre-compaction has an influence on the compaction behavior. This can be concluded from the fact that for the WF the fiber volume content e.g. at 4 bar is not the same for all experiments, even though the pre-compaction was exceeded.

Figure 4: Hydrodynamic compaction caused by transverse flow with increasing pressure drops. (The reachable pressure drops are correlated to pressure losses in the tube leading to the cavity. The higher the permeability, the smaller the pressure drop reachable)

The hydrodynamic compaction leads to a pore space reduction, which causes a transverse permeability decrease. This can be seen in Figure 5, which is based on the same experiments as Figure 4. The diagrams show that the transverse permeability is negatively correlated to the fiber volume content. For the lowest initial fiber volume content of the WF, the transverse permeability at 4 bar pressure drop is more than 80 % smaller than the transverse permeability measured at 0.5 bar pressure drop.

The diagrams in Figure 5 show a further effect. When looking at the NCF-experiments performed at the highest initial fiber volume content ($> 54\%$), one can see that with increasing pressure drop almost no additional compaction is given (this was already noticed in Figure 4). Despite this, the transverse permeability at a pressure drop of 2.5 bar is 14 % smaller than the transverse permeability measured at a pressure drop of 0.5 bar. Also, during the WF-experiments performed at the highest initial fiber volume content ($> 54\%$), the first pressure drop increases caused transverse permeability reductions, even though the pre-compaction was not exceeded. Since no increase of the total fiber volume content is given, the question is which effect causes the transverse permeability decrease with increasing pressure drop. The explanation for this effect is visualized in Figure 6. The pressure drop, occurring during saturated transverse flow, induces an inhomogeneous distribution of the compaction forces affecting the textile. According to Terzhagi's principle [18], the effective compaction pressure acting on the textile σ_{eff} will develop opposed to the fluid pressure σ_{Fluid} and at every point within the flow-through textile their sum will correspond to the total injection pressure σ_{total} :

$$\sigma_{total} = \sigma_{eff} + \sigma_{pore} \quad (2)$$

This leads to inhomogeneous compaction and hence, the fiber volume content distribution will be inhomogeneous. With rising pressure drop, this inhomogeneity increases. If the total fiber volume content remains constant, this means that in some zones the fiber volume content will decrease while it will increase in other zones. Since the transverse permeability is directly correlated to the fiber volume content it will also be inhomogeneously distributed. Thereby, the transverse permeability decreases are too high to be compensated by the permeability increases in other zones. Correspondingly, the total transverse permeability is reduced with increasing pressure drops.

The heterogenization effect also explains why the experiments performed at the different initial fiber volume contents do not perfectly line up, as one would expect if the increase of the total fiber volume content would be the only reason for the permeability reduction. The results of the study show that both, the total deformation and the heterogenization effect, are too strong to be neglected.

Figure 5: Reduction of transverse permeability caused by hydrodynamic compaction.

Figure 6: Influence of the heterogenization of the fiber volume distribution on the transverse permeability.

As a consequence, the simple description of the transverse permeability only as a function of the total fiber volume content can lead to errors in the description of the saturated zone when simulating the transverse impregnation of preforms. A possible alternative would be two describe the transverse permeability as a function of the fiber volume content and the pressure drop. This was exemplarily done for the WF. The experimental data shown in the top diagram of Figure 5 was fitted by least square method to the base function

$$f(x, y) = B \cdot e^{(-x/C)} \cdot e^{(-y/D)} \quad (3)$$

with x and y being the fiber volume content and the pressure drop and B , C , and D being the fitting variables. Further theoretical data points can be considered. They result e.g. from the fact that at 0 or 100 % fiber volume content no compaction can occur and therefore, the permeability must be equal. Such theoretical data points were neglected in favor of a better fitting of the experimental data.

The resulting function for the WF is

$$K3(V_F, \Delta p) = 9.021 \times 10^{-10} m^2 \cdot e^{\frac{V_F}{0.080}} \cdot e^{\frac{\Delta p \cdot bar^{-1}}{4.178}} \quad (4)$$

The resulting function for the WF is

$$K3(V_F, \Delta p) = 5.753 \times 10^{-09} m^2 \cdot e^{\frac{V_F}{0.066}} \cdot e^{\frac{\Delta p \cdot bar^{-1}}{5.487}} \quad (5)$$

The function is shown as a 3D-plot in Figure 7. It has to be mentioned that this function contradicts the original definition of the permeability, defined by the law of Darcy, since the law only describes flows through rigid structures and therefore does not involve the possibility of a pressure-dependence. However, the term transverse permeability is maintained to impede confusion.

Figure 7: 3D plot of the correlation of transverse permeability, pressure drop and fiber volume content for the woven fabric.

The hydrodynamic compaction and the resulting transverse permeability reduction can have severe effects on the efficiency of transverse impregnation processes. Equation (1) states that a flow rate increase requires a pressure drop increase if all other parameters remain unchanged. But the pressure drop increase also causes hydrodynamic compaction, which reduces permeability. Hence, the linear correlation stated by Equation 1 is not realistic during transverse impregnation of textiles. Figure 8 shows a degressive correlation and a stagnation of the flow rates reached by increasing pressure drops during the experiments. In some of the experiments even flow rate reductions resulting from pressure drop increases were measured – this means, the transverse permeability reduction over-compensated the pressure drop increase. Such effects must be avoided when designing a transverse impregnation process. Correspondingly, the textile impregnation behavior has to be known to impede inefficient process parameter selection.

Figure 8: Stagnation of flow rate increase caused by hydrodynamic compaction.

5.2 Influence of flow acceleration on the transverse impregnation behavior

The results presented in section 5.1 show the negative influence of the hydrodynamic compaction on the transverse impregnation speed. Yet, it is known that the pressure, required to compact a textile to a certain fiber volume content, depends on the compaction velocity [3, 19]. Accordingly, textile compaction contains a visco-elastic component. The target of the presented study was to investigate if the viscoelasticity can be utilized to reduce the negative influence of hydrodynamic compaction on the transverse impregnation.

The approach to utilize the viscoelasticity is as follows: Instead of slowly increasing the pressure drop, the pressure drop is abruptly increased. The viscoelasticity will cause a time delay in the

compaction reaction so that in the first seconds after the pressure increase a very high flow rate is reached.

To investigate the benefit of this approach the textile behavior of the woven fabric (WF) was investigated with the system presented in section 4. In a first experiment the usual approach of slow and stepwise pressure drop increase up to 2.5 bar was performed. Therefore, the textile had enough time to hydrodynamically compact. The corresponding pressure drop development is illustrated in the upper left diagram of Figure 9 and the experiment is referred to as experiment A.

In a second experiment the pressure drop was abruptly increased to 2.5 bar, presuming that the time is too short for a strong hydrodynamic compaction. The corresponding pressure drop development is illustrated in the bottom left diagram of Figure 9 and the experiment is referred to as experiment B.

The focus of comparison is on the 25 seconds before the final pressure drop of 2.5 bar is reached. In both cases more than 90 % of the final pressure is reached within the first 5 s, but it takes another 20 s until a full equilibrium is reached and all compaction effects are completed. For the flow rate two outcomes are possible:

- If the textile is perfectly elastic, without any viscous component, then the following should be true: the pressure drop in experiment A is consistently higher than in experiment B until the final pressure drop of 2.5 bar is reached. Figure 8 shows, that in this pressure range every pressure drop increase leads to a flow rate increase, even though hydrodynamic compaction occurs. Accordingly, the flow rate in experiment A should be consistently higher than in experiment B.
- If – as it is presumed – the textile provides a viscoelastic behavior, the fast pressure drop increase will temporarily lead to higher flow rates, because the compaction is delayed and the pressure drop acts on a less compacted preform.

The both right diagrams in Figure 9 show the flow rate development during the 25 s which are within the focus of comparison. Indeed, a very strong increase of the flow rate is given in experiment B, whereas the flow rate in experiment A shows only a very slight overshoot. It takes 25 seconds until the flow rates equalizes and in this time range about 11 ml more have flown through the WF in experiment B. Related to the flown-through cross section and assuming a fiber volume content of about 50 % this corresponds to an additional flow movement of 1.5 mm. This confirms that the textile compaction is delayed to the pressure increase and thus, a fast acceleration of flow can be beneficial during transverse impregnation.

Figure 9: Positive influence of a high flow acceleration on the transverse impregnation of the woven fabric.

6 CONCLUSION

Within the study the influence of pressure drop, flow rate and flow acceleration on the textile impregnation behavior in transverse direction was investigated. A woven fabric and a non-crimp fabric were considered. The experiments show the following:

- Pressure drop increases during transverse flow cause remarkable hydrodynamic compaction.
- The hydrodynamic compaction is accompanied by a heterogenization of the fiber volume content distribution.
- Both, total compaction and heterogenization cause a permeability reduction.
- The permeability reduction results in a stagnation of the flow rate increase reachable with a pressure drop increase.
- The viscoelastic compaction behavior of textiles can be utilized for faster transverse impregnation.

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